

ANALYSIS OF THE NEED FOR DEVELOPING THE RANI LEARNING MODEL TO IMPROVE DESCRIPTIVE WRITING SKILLS

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Abstract

This study was motivated by the low level of descriptive writing skills among elementary school students, particularly in terms of idea development, paragraph organization, and spelling accuracy, as identified through a preliminary study in the fourth grade at SDN Pasirjaya. The learning environment, which is still oriented toward final results without focusing on the writing process, has resulted in students being unable to write systematically and elaboratively. This study aims to analyze the need to develop the RANI (Readiness, Analyze, Name, Interpret) Learning Model as the basis for designing a process-based writing learning model. The research used a qualitative approach with a preliminary study design (needs analysis). Data sources included 28 fourth-grade students and 12 teachers at SDN Pasirjaya, with data collection techniques in the form of diagnostic tests, learning observations, interviews, and documentation. The data were analyzed descriptively through reduction, presentation, and conclusion drawing. The results showed that 43% of students were in the category of adequate writing ability, 29% were poor, and only 28% were good, with an average score of 68. These findings indicate the need for a structured, explicit, and process-based learning model as the basis for developing the RANI Model in the next stage of research.

Keywords: *Elementary School, Learning Model Development, RANI Model, Writing Skills.*

INTRODUCTION

Writing skills are a key component in the development of 21st-century literacy, which plays a role in building students' critical thinking, communication, and knowledge construction skills (Graham, 2020; Graham et al., 2018). At the elementary school level, writing instruction lays the foundation for academic literacy development and learning performance across various subjects (McLean & Kate Griffiths, 2022). Writing is not merely a transcription activity, but rather a complex cognitive process involving planning, organizing ideas, developing content, and revising (Graham, 2020; Hayes, 2012a; Shaw, 2022). In this context, writing descriptive texts requires keen observation skills, appropriate word choice, and coherent and detailed paragraph structure. However, various international studies show that many elementary school students still have difficulty producing structured and in-depth texts. A recent meta-analysis by Graham et al., (2025) confirms that the quality of students' writing is greatly influenced by explicit and structured learning strategies. In addition, research by Graham (2023) and Rathé et al., (2022) shows that writing ability at the elementary school level is closely correlated with planning and self-regulation skills in the writing process. These findings indicate that writing instruction needs to be process-oriented so that students obtain adequate cognitive scaffolding.

A process-based approach and explicit strategies in writing instruction have been shown to be effective in improving the quality of students' writing (Flunger et al., 2019; Margarida Veiga-Simão et al., 2022). Systematic instructional scaffolding helps students through the stages of thinking before writing, such as observing, analyzing, organizing ideas, and interpreting information (Dockrell et al., 2016; Han, 2024). From a social constructivist perspective, this process is in line with Vygotsky's theory about the importance of mediation and structured support in students' proximal development zone. In Indonesia, research on writing instruction in elementary schools still shows a predominance of product-oriented approaches, with an emphasis on the final written product rather than the underlying cognitive processes (Guo et al., 2021; Yulistiani & Indihadi, 2020). Initial observations in several elementary schools show that students are often asked to write immediately without going through the stages of learning readiness, object exploration, or vocabulary reinforcement. As a result, the descriptive texts produced tend

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to be less detailed and unsystematic. This condition shows a gap between international research findings on the effectiveness of process-based learning and learning practices in the field. Recent research also emphasizes the importance of learning models that explicitly integrate stages of thinking into a systematic syntactic framework (Kennedy & Shiel, 2025; Masrul et al., 2023). An effective learning model must be able to facilitate student readiness, the ability to analyze information, the organization of concepts (naming/categorizing), and interpretation and written expression. However, to date, there has not been much research specifically developing a structured learning model with these stages in the context of teaching descriptive writing in Indonesian elementary schools. Based on these problems and gaps, a needs analysis is required as the initial stage in developing the RANI (Readiness, Analyze, Name, Interpret) Learning Model. The needs analysis aims to identify the actual learning conditions, the needs of teachers and students, and the characteristics of descriptive text writing in elementary schools. This stage is important in research and development (R&D) to ensure that the model designed is based on empirical data and is appropriate to the user context (Borg & Gall, 1984; Mahoney, 2013; O'Sullivan et al., 2012).

Theoretically, this study contributes to enriching the study of developing process-based writing learning models and explicit strategies at the elementary school level. This study also expands the integration of constructivism theory and self-regulation approaches in writing learning design. Practically, the results of this needs analysis provide an empirical basis for designing a relevant, contextual, and implementable RANI Learning Model. This model is expected to be an innovative alternative in improving elementary school students' descriptive writing skills in a more systematic and meaningful way. Thus, the needs analysis for the development of the RANI Learning Model is a strategic step in responding to the challenges of writing learning in elementary schools while preparing a conceptual and empirical basis for the development of innovative and evidence-based learning models.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Writing is a complex language skill because it involves simultaneous cognitive, linguistic, and metacognitive processes. According to Graham et al., (2018), writing is not just an activity of pouring ideas into text, but also involves the processes of planning, organizing ideas, constructing sentences, and repeated revision. Therefore, effective writing learning needs to be designed as a systematic and continuous process so that students are able to develop ideas in a coherent and consistent manner. Previous studies have shown that a process-based approach to writing instruction has a positive impact on improving the quality of students' writing. Research conducted by Kim and Graham (2022) shows that the quality of elementary school students' writing is greatly influenced by explicit teaching of writing strategies, including planning, idea development, and revision strategies. The study also emphasizes the importance of self-regulation in the writing process, in which students need to be trained to monitor and evaluate their writing independently.

In addition to the process-based approach, the theoretical framework of social constructivism is also an important foundation in writing learning. In this perspective, learning is viewed as an active process that occurs through social interaction and guidance from more competent individuals. Lundgren (2023) explains the concept of the zone of proximal development (ZPD), which emphasizes the importance of scaffolding or gradual support from teachers in helping students achieve higher levels of ability. In the context of writing learning, scaffolding can be realized through providing text examples, discussing ideas, providing guidance in structuring writing, and giving constructive feedback on students' writing. However, several studies also show that writing learning practices in elementary schools still tend to be oriented towards the final product. Teachers often place more emphasis on the results of writing than on the process students go through in producing the writing. As a result, students have fewer opportunities to develop ideas in depth, make revisions, or reflect on the quality of their writing. This condition causes students' writing skills to develop in a limited and suboptimal manner.

On the other hand, a number of studies highlight the importance of integrating learning strategies that can develop students' motivation, self-regulation, and critical thinking skills in writing. Collaborative and reflective learning approaches have been proven to increase student engagement in the writing process. However, there are still limitations in research that specifically develops a structured and contextual process-based writing learning model at the elementary school level, especially in the context of education in Indonesia. Based on this literature review, a research gap can be identified regarding the need to develop a writing learning model that not only emphasizes the written product but also facilitates students' thinking and self-regulation processes in a systematic manner. Therefore, this study aims to examine the need to develop a more structured and contextual writing learning model, which is expected to contribute conceptually and practically to improving the quality of writing learning in elementary schools.

METHOD

This research is a preliminary study within the framework of research and development (R&D) that aims to analyze the need to develop the RANI Learning Model in teaching descriptive writing. The approach used is qualitative with an exploratory case study design. This design was chosen because the study sought to gain an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon of descriptive text writing in a real context before designing the learning model to be developed. Case studies allow researchers to explore learning conditions holistically and contextually in natural settings (Ali & Asrori, 2022; J. Creswell, 2010). The preliminary study stage in development research serves to identify problems, user needs, and learning context characteristics as the basis for product design (Borg & Gall, 1984). The research was conducted at SDN Pasirjaya with a focus on Indonesian language learning in fourth grade. The research subjects consisted of 28 fourth-grade students and 12 teachers who taught at the school, with fourth-grade teachers as the main informants. The subjects were selected using purposive sampling, which is selecting participants who are directly involved in teaching descriptive text writing so that they can provide relevant and in-depth information related to the needs of developing a learning model (Baran, 2022; J. W. Creswell, 2019; Jacobsen, 2023)

Data collection was conducted through classroom observation, in-depth interviews, and document analysis. Observations were conducted non-participatively to obtain a realistic picture of the descriptive text writing learning process, including the strategies used by teachers, the learning stages, and the form of scaffolding provided to students. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with fourth-grade teachers to explore information about learning obstacles, students' difficulties in writing descriptive texts, and the need for a more systematic learning model. In addition, several students were also interviewed to understand their learning experiences. Document analysis was conducted on the Lesson Plan (RPP), the textbooks used, and the students' writing to see the suitability between the planning, implementation, and learning outcomes. The use of these various techniques aimed to increase the depth and accuracy of the data through triangulation (Huan et al., 2021).

The data obtained was analyzed using interactive analysis techniques, including data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing and verification (Miles et al., 2014). The analysis was conducted thematically to identify patterns of problems and learning needs that formed the basis for the development of the RANI Learning Model. The validity of the data was ensured through triangulation of techniques and sources, as well as member checks with informants to ensure that the researchers' interpretations were consistent with the participants' experiences (Yin, 2018). The results of this preliminary study produced a mapping of descriptive text writing learning needs at SDN Pasirjaya, including the identification of gaps between current learning practices and the principles of process-based writing learning recommended in the literature (Graham, 2023). These findings form the empirical and conceptual basis for designing a RANI Learning Model syntax that is relevant, contextual, and appropriate for the characteristics of elementary school students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Overview of Students' Writing Skills

The results of the initial diagnostic test showed that the writing skills of fourth-grade students at SDN Pasirjaya were still in the moderate category. Of the 28 students, 28% were in the good category, 43% in the fair category, and 29% in the poor category, with a class average score of 68. This distribution shows that the majority of students have not yet reached an optimal level of writing skills. The dominance of the fair category indicates that students have basic skills but are not yet able to develop their writing in an elaborate, coherent, and systematic manner. The data from the initial diagnostic test is presented in graph form to provide a clearer visual picture, as shown in the following figure.

Figure 1. Data hasil tes diagnostik awal

Upon further analysis, the average score of 68 indicates that students' writing skills are still at the minimum passing level. Quantitatively, the proportion of students in the poor category (29%) shows that nearly one-third of students require intensive intervention, while those in the fair category (43%) need reinforcement in order to improve to the good category. This condition indicates a gap in writing skills among students that needs to be addressed through differentiated and structured learning strategies. Qualitatively, analysis of students' writing shows that weaknesses lie not only in mechanical aspects such as spelling and punctuation, but also in the ability to develop ideas in depth and organize them into a logical text structure. Students' writing is generally still simple and descriptive, lacking rich sensory details and optimal use of vocabulary variation. This shows that students' thinking processes in writing have not yet fully developed to the stage of elaboration and reflection.

These findings are in line with Hayes (2012b), Kim & Graham (2022), and Schneier (2023) who states that writing is a complex cognitive process involving planning, translating ideas, and reviewing. When students are not systematically facilitated in these three stages, the resulting writing tends to be superficial and unstructured. In addition, Abdel Latif, (2021) and Bowen & Van Waes (2020) emphasizes that the quality of elementary school students' writing is greatly influenced by the extent to which teachers provide explicit instruction on writing strategies, including planning and revision. Thus, the general picture of the writing abilities of fourth-grade students at SDN Pasirjaya shows that the problems that arise are not solely caused by a lack of mastery of language rules, but also by the suboptimal process-based learning that develops students' cognitive strategies and self-regulation. This condition emphasizes the urgency of developing a more systematic, explicit, and process-oriented writing learning model as a strategic step to continuously improve the quality of students' writing.

Motivation, Self-Regulation, and Writing Quality

The results of the observation show that some students lack confidence in writing and tend to complete assignments without making corrections or revisions. Some students appear hesitant when asked to reread their writing, and some even submit their work without checking for spelling errors or completeness. This condition indicates a low level of self-regulation in the writing process, especially in the monitoring and evaluation stages. In fact, the ability to plan, monitor, and reflect on writing is an important part of mature writing skills. Theoretically, self-regulation in writing includes the ability to set goals, manage time, monitor progress, and revise independently.

In their study, Grace Kim (2022) and Marnel Sterk et al., (2025) emphasize that the quality of elementary school students' writing is greatly influenced by the self-regulation strategies explicitly taught by teachers. Students who are accustomed to planning before writing and reviewing their writing tend to produce longer, more structured, and more elaborate texts than students who write without planning. In addition to cognitive aspects, motivational factors also play an important role. Oliveri et al., (2021) found that intrinsic motivation has a positive correlation with the quality and length of students' texts. Students with high motivation show greater perseverance in completing writing tasks, are more open to feedback, and are more willing to make revisions. Conversely, low self-efficacy makes students give up easily and consider writing a difficult and burdensome task (Aull, 2020).

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The conditions found in the fourth grade of Pasirjaya Public Elementary School show that writing instruction has not fully encouraged the growth of students' self-confidence and independence in learning. The writing process is still perceived as a one-stage activity (one draft writing), rather than a gradual process involving reflection and improvement. In fact, according to Cotos (2023) and Hartwell & Aull (2024), motivation and self-efficacy are important predictors of writing success at the elementary school level. When students feel capable and receive adequate support, the quality of their writing tends to improve significantly. Thus, improving writing skills requires more than just strengthening technical and structural aspects; it must also be accompanied by pedagogical strategies that foster motivation and self-regulation. Supportive, collaborative, and process-based learning through formative feedback, opportunities for revision, and self-reflection can help students build confidence and responsibility for the quality of their writing. These efforts form an important foundation in the development of a learning model that not only improves written products but also shapes independent and reflective writers.

Implications for the Development of the Readiness, Analyse, Name, Interpret (RANI) Model

Overall, the results of the study show a gap between writing instruction practices in the fourth grade at SDN Pasirjaya and the latest international research recommendations. Instruction is still oriented toward the final product, while process stages such as planning, organizing ideas, revising, and reflecting are not yet systematically facilitated. The lack of explicit strategies, scaffolding, and formative feedback has prevented students from developing their writing skills optimally, both cognitively and metacognitively. From a social constructivist perspective, Gozali et al., (2024) and Li & Li (2022) asserts that students' cognitive development occurs through social interaction and gradual guidance (scaffolding). This principle is relevant to the needs of writing instruction, which places teachers as facilitators of the process, not merely evaluators of the final results. This theoretical support is reinforced by the findings of Graham, Steve, Hebert, and Harris, Karen R. (2020) in *The Elementary School Journal*, which show that the integration of explicit planning, formative evaluation, and systematic strategy learning has a significant impact on improving the quality of elementary school students' writing.

Furthermore, a comprehensive study by Knight et al., (2020) in the *Review of Educational Research* confirms that writing quality is greatly influenced by explicit teaching of self-regulation strategies and text structure. Students who received structured instruction on how to plan, organize, and revise their writing showed significant improvements in cohesion, elaboration of ideas, and text length. These findings reinforce the argument that process-based learning models are more effective than traditional product-oriented approaches. In addition, research by Dunn (2021) and Zhang & Yu (2024) in *Contemporary Educational Psychology on Self-Regulated Strategy Development (SRSD)* shows that learning that integrates strategy, modeling, and self-reflection can consistently improve writing quality. This shows that the development of the RANI Model needs to adopt the principles of strategy learning and self-regulation as core components. Based on empirical findings in the field and international literature support, the development of the RANI Model is relevant and contextual to address the needs of fourth-grade students at SDN Pasirjaya. This model is expected to integrate the stages of Readiness, Analyze, Name, and Interpret as a learning cycle that facilitates explicit planning, text structure analysis, systematic idea development, and continuous reflection and revision. Conceptually and empirically, this study reinforces the urgency of developing a structured process-based writing learning model that not only improves the quality of writing products but also builds students' self-regulation, motivation, and learning independence in elementary school in a sustainable manner.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of a preliminary study conducted in the fourth grade of SDN Pasirjaya, it can be confirmed that the problems in learning to write do not primarily stem from limitations in the individual capacities of students, but rather from the lack of a pedagogical ecosystem that facilitates a systematic, explicit, and continuous writing process. This finding repositions the understanding of the low quality of students' writing: weaknesses in developing ideas, constructing coherent paragraphs, and applying spelling rules correctly are not indications of cognitive limitations alone, but reflections of a learning approach that is still oriented towards the final product without structured stages of planning, development, and revision. Reflectively, this research produced new information in the form of mapping contextual and specific pedagogical needs at SDN Pasirjaya, namely the urgency of developing an integrated process-based writing learning model. This model needs to combine initial idea stimulation, idea mapping, step-by-step writing, and reflective revision supported by formative feedback as a unified learning system. Thus, the contribution of this study does not stop at describing the factual conditions but shows the position of research as a conceptual and empirical basis for designing more effective pedagogical interventions. The implication is that improving writing competence in elementary schools requires a transformation of the learning

approach from an outcome-oriented approach to a structured and continuous process-oriented approach. This conclusion also confirms that efforts to improve the quality of students' writing must begin with the reconstruction of the learning design, so that this research has strategic significance as a basis for the development of an evidence-based learning model at the advanced research stage.

REFERENCES

- Abdel Latif, M. M. M. (2021). Remodeling writers' composing processes: Implications for writing assessment. *Assessing Writing*, 50, 100547. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2021.100547>
- Ali, M., & Asrori, M. (2022). *Metodologi dan aplikasi riset pendidikan*. books.google.com. <https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=C4h-EAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=metodologi&ots=Ox0mF0P0e1&sig=9bxx8Hm5edesY5MRw1jx-OqkyM>
- Aull, L. (2020). Student-centered assessment and online writing feedback: Technology in a time of crisis. *Assessing Writing*, 46, 100483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2020.100483>
- Baleghizadeh, S., & Jafari, R. (n.d.). *The Effect of Strategy-Based Instruction on Iranian EFL Learners' Writing Achievement*.
- Baran, M. L. (2022). Mixed Methods Research Design. In *Research Anthology on Innovative Research Methodologies and Utilization Across Multiple Disciplines* (pp. 312–333). IGI Global Scientific Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-3881-7.ch017>
- Borg, W. R., & Gall, M. D. (1984). Educational research: An introduction. *British Journal of Educational Studies*, 32(3). <https://philpapers.org/rec/BORERA-2>
- Bowen, N., & Van Waes, L. (2020). Exploring Revisions in Academic Text: Closing the Gap Between Process and Product Approaches in Digital Writing. *Written Communication*, 37(3), 322–364. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0741088320916508>
- Cotos, E. (2023). Automated Feedback on Writing. In O. Kruse, C. Rapp, C. M. Anson, K. Benetos, E. Cotos, A. Devitt, & A. Shibani (Eds.), *Digital Writing Technologies in Higher Education: Theory, Research, and Practice* (pp. 347–364). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-36033-6_22
- Creswell, J. (2010). *A. Metodologi Penelitian*. (Query date: 2024-05-14 13:41:05). <http://digilib.ikipgripta.ac.id/1301/4/BAB%20III%20METODOLOGI%20PENELITIAN.pdf>
- Creswell, J. W. (2019). Mixed Methods and Survey Research in Family Medicine and Community Health. *Chinese General Practice*, 22(23), 2780–2785. <https://doi.org/10.12114/j.issn.1007-9572.2019.00.397>
- Dockrell, J. E., Marshall, C. R., & Wyse, D. (2016). Teachers' reported practices for teaching writing in England. *Reading and Writing*, 29(3), 409–434. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11145-015-9605-9>
- Dunn, M. (2021). The Challenges of Struggling Writers: Strategies That Can Help. *Education Sciences*, 11(12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11120795>
- Flunger, B., Mayer, A., & Umbach, N. (2019). Beneficial for some or for everyone? Exploring the effects of an autonomy-supportive intervention in the real-life classroom. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 111(2), 210–234. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000284>
- Gozali, I., Wijaya, A. R. T., Lie, A., Cahyono, B. Y., & Suryati, N. (2024). Leveraging the potential of ChatGPT as an automated writing evaluation (AWE) tool: Students' feedback literacy development and AWE tools integration framework. *The JALT CALL Journal*, 20(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.29140/jaltcall.v20n1.1200>
- Grace Kim, Y.-S. (2022). Do Written Language Bursts Mediate the Relations of Language, Cognitive, and Transcription Skills to Writing Quality? *Written Communication*, 39(2), 200–227. <https://doi.org/10.1177/07410883211068753>
- Graham, S. (2020). The Sciences of Reading and Writing Must Become More Fully Integrated. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 55(Query date: 2024-09-15 18:39:00). <https://doi.org/10.1002/rrq.332>
- Graham, S. (2023). Writer(s)-within-Community Model of Writing as a Lens for Studying the Teaching of Writing. In *The Routledge International Handbook of Research on Writing* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- Graham, S., Cao, Y., Kim, Y.-S. G., Lee, J., Tate, T., Collins, P., Cho, M., Moon, Y., Chung, H. Q., & Olson, C. B. (2025). Effective writing instruction for students in grades 6 to 12: A best evidence meta-analysis. *Reading and Writing*, 38(4), 1–46. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11145-024-10539-2>

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- Graham, S., MacArthur, C. A., & Hebert, M. A. (2018). *Best Practices in Writing Instruction, Third Edition*. Guilford Publications.
- Guo, W., Bai, B., & Song, H. (2021). Influences of process-based instruction on students' use of self-regulated learning strategies in EFL writing. *System*, *101*, 102578. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2021.102578>
- Han, L. (2024). Metacognitive Writing Strategy Instruction in the EFL Context: Focus on Writing Performance and Motivation. *Sage Open*, *14*(2), 21582440241257081. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440241257081>
- Hartwell, K., & Aull, L. (2024). Navigating innovation and equity in writing assessment. *Assessing Writing*, *61*, 100873. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2024.100873>
- Hayes, J. R. (2012a). Modeling and Remodeling Writing. *Written Communication*, *29*(3), 369–388. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0741088312451260>
- Hayes, J. R. (2012b). Modeling and Remodeling Writing. *Written Communication*, *29*(3), 369–388. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0741088312451260>
- Huan, Y., Liang, T., Li, H., & Zhang, C. (2021). A systematic method for assessing progress of achieving sustainable development goals: A case study of 15 countries. *Science of the Total Environment*, (Query date: 2024-06-27 04:50:56). <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0048969720354048>
- Jacobsen, M. (2023). Educational design research: Grappling with methodological fit. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, (Query date: 2024-06-30 07:13:01). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-023-10282-5>
- Kennedy, E., & Shiel, G. (2025). *Teaching and Assessing Writing in the Primary School: A Whole School Approach* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003303510>
- Kim, Y.-S. G., & Graham, S. (2022). Expanding the Direct and Indirect Effects Model of Writing (DIEW): Reading–writing relations, and dynamic relations as a function of measurement/dimensions of written composition. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, *114*(2), 215–238. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000564>
- Knight, S., Shibani, A., Abel, S., Gibson, A., & Ryan, P. (2020). AcaWriter: A Learning Analytics Tool for Formative Feedback on Academic Writing. *Journal of Writing Research*, *12*(vol. 12 issue 1), 141–186. <https://doi.org/10.17239/jowr-2020.12.01.06>
- Li, J., & Li, M. (2022). Assessing L2 writing in the digital age: Opportunities and challenges. *Journal of Second Language Writing, L2 Writing Assessment in the Digital Age*, *57*, 100913. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jslw.2022.100913>
- Lundgren, A. (2023). The Zone of Proximal Development and Content Area Instruction for Middle School English Language Learner Students: A Phenomenological Study. *Doctoral Dissertations and Projects*. <https://digitalcommons.liberty.edu/doctoral/4818>
- Mahoney, J. (2013). *Teaching Business Ethics in the UK, Europe and the USA: A Comparative Study*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Margarida Veiga-Simão, A., Oliveira, S., Silva-Moreira, J., & Itália Temudo, M. (2022). Assessing the Efficacy and Social Validity of *CriaTivo*, a Curriculum-Based Intervention to Promote Self-Regulation of Writing in Portuguese Elementary Education. *Sage Open*, *12*(3), 21582440221117133. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440221117133>
- Marnel Sterk, F., Van Goch, M., Burke, M., & Van Der Tuin, I. (2025). Popularization Writing Skills Development: A Longitudinal Case Study of the Writing Process and Writing Outcomes in Nine Undergraduate Interdisciplinary Students. *Written Communication*, *42*(4), 966–998. <https://doi.org/10.1177/07410883251349204>
- Masrul, M., Gunadi, R. A. A., Aswir, A., Hamdani, B., & Yuliani, S. (2023). Incorporating Strategy Instruction (SI) and Strategy-Based Writing Instruction (SBI) to Enhancing Students' Writing Abilities. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, *14*(4), 1117–1126.
- McLean, E., & Kate Griffiths, C. (2022). *Writing and Writing Instruction: An Overview of the Literature*. *Literature Review*. Australian Education Research Organisation Limited. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED674031>
- Miles, M. B., Huberman, A. M., & Saldana, J. (2014). *Qualitative data analysis: A methods sourcebook*. (No Title).
- Oliveri, M. E., Mislevy, R. J., & Slomp, D. (2021). Principled Development of Workplace English Communication Part 1: A Sociocognitive Framework. *The Journal of Writing Analytics*, *5*(1), 34–70. <https://doi.org/10.37514/JWA-J.2021.5.1.02>
- O'Sullivan, P., Smith, M., & Esposito, M. (2012). *Business Ethics: A Critical Approach: Integrating Ethics Across the Business World*. Routledge.

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- Rathé, S., Torbeyns, J., De Smedt, B., & Verschaffel, L. (2022). Longitudinal associations between spontaneous number focusing tendencies, numerical abilities, and mathematics achievement in 4- to 7-year-olds. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, *114*(1), 37–55. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000665>
- Schneier, J. (2023). Modeling Mobile Writing: Applying Sociocognitive Models of Writing to Mobile Contexts. *Written Communication*, *40*(1), 3–29. <https://doi.org/10.1177/07410883221131543>
- Shaw, S. R. (2022). *Reaching and Teaching Students Who Don't Qualify for Special Education: Strategies for the Inclusive Education of Diverse Learners*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003133896>
- Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case study research and applications* (Vol. 6). Sage Thousand Oaks, CA.
- Yulistiani, D., & Indihadi, D. (2020). Keterampilan Menulis Teks Eksplanasi dengan Menggunakan Media Gambar Berseri. *PEDADIDAKTIKA: Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Pendidikan Guru Sekolah Dasar*, *7*(3), 228–234. <https://doi.org/10.17509/pedadidaktika.v7i3.25625>
- Zhang, E. D., & Yu, S. (2024). Understanding L2 student writers' self-assessment in digital multimodal composing: A process-oriented approach. *System*, *121*, 103219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2024.103219>